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Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

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D5.2 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Socio-Economic Impact Assessment (SEIA) of the MegaRoller device

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MegaRoller is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at developing and demonstrating a Power Take-off unit (PTO) able to increase the output from the few 100 kW range to a full 1 MW range. The project will generate extensive know-how in the area of PTO design and control systems, with the aim to decrease the levelized cost of energy of next generation Oscillating Wave Surge Converter devices.

The project *Work Package 5 – Validation & Impact Evaluation* focuses on demonstrating that the models and technical solutions produced in the project meet the objectives issued regarding PTO performance, power quality, reliability, and cost reduction. Together with demonstration and validation activities (Tasks 5.1-5.3) and life-cycle cost assessment (Task 5.5), the project includes the evaluation of the environmental and socio-economic impacts expected from the MegaRoller device (Task 5.4).

The present report builds on the *Deliverable 2.6*¹ which presented a method for EIA and SEIA for wave energy (WE) projects. The method was based on an exhaustive literature review on previous EIAs for similar installations, leading to the identification of a set of receptors and stressors potentially related to the development of nearshore wave energy devices, mitigation measures to be implemented, and monitoring techniques to be carried out.

This report presents the development of an *Environmental and Socioeconomic Impact Assessment Tool (ESIAT)* and its application to the MegaRoller installation². The aim is for ESIAT to provide the environmental and socioeconomic impact assessment of the MegaRoller installation (including all stages of its development: preparation, construction, operation, decommissioning), allowing the developer, managers, and regulators for a quicker and more informed decision-making with regards to the mitigation of impacts that might come from the MegaRoller and to the monitoring of such impacts.

The ESIAT was developed based on the findings from D2.6 and from further literature review carried out to include more recent developments on EIAs and monitoring activities undertaken for Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) projects and especially at WE installations. The impact assessment is provided by the ESIAT as a very extensive file; therefore, this report summarizes the assessment of the most significant impacts, the full assessment being attached to this report as Annex 1.

¹ MegaRoller project *Deliverable 2.6 – Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Socioeconomic Impact Assessment (SEIA) models*, available at <https://zenodo.org/record/3372479#.Xw3KtyhKi70>.

² The MegaRoller installation includes the MegaRoller device and all support structures such as the foundation, moorings, and electrical cable.

List of Acronyms

ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
AM	Adaptive Management
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, Depth
EMEC	European Marine Energy Centre
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
ESIAT	Environmental and Socioeconomic Impact Assessment Tool
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
MRE	Marine Renewable Energy
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
SEIA	Socioeconomic Impact Assessment
WE	Wave Energy
WEC	Wave Energy Converter

1 THE EIA PROCESS

The EIA is an environmental management instrument implemented worldwide to ensure that the environmental implications of a certain action are considered before decision making in a given project. In the EU, the EIA must abide to the EIA Directive (EU, 2011, 2014) which identifies the projects subject to mandatory EIA (defined in Annex I of the Directive), and those for which EIA can be requested at the discretion of the Member States (defined in Annex II of the Directive). Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) projects are considered within Annex II of the EIA Directive, under the category *Energy industry: a) Industrial installations for the production of electricity (...)*.

In the EU, although the majority of MRE developments require EIA to ensure the effects of the development on the environment, biological and physical processes, EIA procedures vary in relation with legal, policy and institutional frameworks in different countries (Leeney et al., 2014). Wave Energy Converter (WEC) projects in full scale are expected to be subject to an EIA process. On the other hand, test sites and small-scale demonstration projects may not be required to carry out a full-scale EIA process since pre-consenting (performed during test site licensing) is usually available.

The EIA process can be summarized into seven main steps (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: EIA process flowchart (adapted from: UNEP, 2002).

During the first step, *Screening*, the national authorities decide whether or not an EIA is needed, considering the project’s characteristics and location and the type and characteristics of potential impacts. If an EIA is required, the next step would be the Scoping.

Scoping identifies the issues that are likely to be of most importance during the EIA so that the study focuses on the significant aspects and avoids time consuming activities.

Baseline characterization gathers information on environmental and socioeconomic baseline conditions in the project's impact area, which will be the basis to predict potential impacts and to develop effective mitigation and monitoring programmes.

Impact Analysis is carried out to assess the scale of potential impacts. It allows to identify/predict which impacts are/will be associated to the project development phase, thus contributing to delineate mitigation measures.

Mitigation measures refers to the actions needed to prevent, minimize, and/or compensate for the predicted adverse effects of projects or to enhance their positive effects. Such measures should be implemented during the impact management stage which aims, among others, at ensuring that mitigation measures are implemented, monitoring the effectiveness of mitigation measures, and undertaking any necessary action when unforeseen impacts occur.

Monitoring is a key step to validate and expand the findings of the initial EIA. A monitoring plan should be drawn for all project phases (preparation, construction, operation, and decommissioning) considering all the information obtained in the previous steps. The monitoring plan must be designed to measure change against baseline conditions or management objectives.

Public involvement throughout the whole process ensures all stakeholders are actively participating in the EIA process and contributing to decision making.

1.1 EIA for the Wave Energy sector

Although Wave Energy (WE) technologies are in an early stage of development, there is a considerable heterogeneity of technologies namely concerning its location and operation principles. While many effects are expected to be common across MRE projects (for example, seabed disturbance by drilling activities, noise created by vessels and machinery), most effects will be project-specific, for example depending on the duration of preparation and construction activities, the type of equipment used in such activities, and on site-specific characteristics such as local hydrodynamics. Consequently, the EIA becomes uncertain for other places or devices due to the scarcity of deployments and monitored projects (Greaves et al., 2016; Mendoza et al., 2019) especially when considering arrays of devices and because usually the projects have not stayed in the water long enough (i.e., several years) to allow monitoring of long-term changes (Copping and Hemery 2020). Thus, the EIA of WE projects remains a challenging task further aggravated by the uncertainty on real negative impacts and especially those with cumulative effects (Frid et al., 2012; Willstedt et al., 2017).

To support the development of the MRE sector, Adaptive Management (AM) has been used to guide the implementation of MRE monitoring programs and has successfully allowed a number of projects worldwide to progress (Copping and Hemery, 2020). The AM is an iterative process that enables projects to be implemented incrementally in the face of uncertainty about potential impacts, and to assist in closing knowledge gaps through rigorous monitoring and review. If information from routine monitoring shows that the level of an effect is likely to cause an unacceptable impact, corrective actions can be taken. Conversely, if monitoring information indicates that risks have been overestimated, monitoring and mitigation requirements may be reduced (Copping and Hemery, 2020).

2 MEGAROLLER EIA AND SEIA MODEL

The MegaRoller project Deliverable 2.6 proposed an environmental and socioeconomic impact assessment standardised model to work as a guideline for developers, managers, and regulators to ease the EIA process for nearshore WE projects allowing for better decision-making.

The environmental and socioeconomic impact assessment model included the identification of potential effects/impacts from nearshore wave energy devices, possible mitigation measures to the impacts, and monitoring activities and parameters.

The following sub-section provides a summary of relevant information presented in D2.6.

The framework of the EIA and SEIA model was adapted from the method developed by Shumchenia et al. (2012). The model was developed following a comprehensive literature review on EIAs for nearshore installations (for example, WE projects, aquaculture cages, pontoons, and other artificial hard structures) (e.g., Boehlert and Gill, 2010; Simas et al. 2013a; Thomsen et al., 2015; Greaves et al., 2016; Iglesias et al., 2018).

The literature review allowed the identification of a set of receptors and stressors potentially related to the development of nearshore WE projects and of impacts (positive and negative) already mentioned for similar nearshore installations.

Twelve key receptors potentially related to the development of nearshore WE projects were identified, grouped into three main categories (factors):

- Physical factors – Receptors: hydrodynamics, water column, seabed, and shoreline
- Biological factors – Receptors: benthic communities, fish and turtles, marine mammals, and birds
- Socioeconomic factors – Receptors: local communities, archaeological/protected sites, landscape/seascape, and economic activities

Physical, biological, and socioeconomic key effects were evaluated through ranking classification criteria adapted from the European Marine Energy Centre (EMEC) guidelines (EMEC, 2013) comprising 6 levels of magnitude of impact (Table 2.1).

After, the interaction of stressors and receptors (within each factor) was crossed in Summary Impact Matrices (a different matrix for each physical, biological, and socioeconomic factors) (Table 2.2). Following, a set of mitigation measures taken from literature were linked to the relevant receptors (Table 2.3). Then, a decision tree method for the identification of the most appropriate monitoring techniques and protocols was delineated based on the parameters that the user chooses for each receptor (Table 2.4; Table 2.5).

Ultimately, the EIA and SEIA model is presented as a stepwise process. In Step 1, the classification of impacts presented in the Summary Impact Matrices (Table 2.2) are adapted to the project features and environmental sensitiveness of the site. This allows the identification, evaluation, and prioritization of impacts, classifying them for each phase of the project development, in a case-by-case analysis, according to the EMEC classification ranking (Table 2.1). In Step 2, mitigation measures (Table 2.3) are assigned to the impacts that have been prioritised in Step 1. In Step 3 the monitoring protocols and techniques to be carried out are presented (Table 2.4). A decision tree (Table 2.5), different for each factor (physical, biological, and socioeconomic), guides the user by offering a set of questions on the receptor, parameter, and phase of development towards the monitoring protocols that determine the monitoring plan across all the receptors considered.

Table 2.1: Magnitude classification of environmental and socioeconomic impacts.

Magnitude of Impact	Description	
	Environmental	Socioeconomic
Major	Degradation to the quality or availability of habitats and/or wildlife with recovery taking more than 2 years	Change to commercial activity leading to a loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Potential short-term effect upon public health/well-being, real risk of injury
Moderate	Change in habitats or species beyond natural variability with good recovery potentially within 2 years	Change to commercial activity leading to a loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Possible, but not likely effect upon public health/well-being, remote risk of injury.
Minor	Change from baseline conditions measurable but within scale of natural variability	Possible nuisance to other activities and some minor influence on income or opportunity. Nuisance, but no lasting effect upon public health/well-being.
Negligible	Change in habitats or species within scope of existing variability and difficult to measure or observe	Noticed by, but not a nuisance to other commercial activities. No discernible effects upon the health and well-being of the public
No Interaction	None	None
Positive	<i>An enhancement of ecosystem or popular parameter</i>	<i>Benefits to local community</i>

Table 2.2: Example of the Summary Impact Matrices. Key: M: impact magnitude; NK: no anticipated key effect; ?: dependent on site-specific features.

Development Phase	Activity	Stressor	Receptor							
			Hydrodynamic System		Water Column		Seabed		Shoreline	
Physical Effects			Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M
Operation	Device deployment	Physical presence of WEC device and structural components	Reduction of wave action	M	Turbulence changes	M	Disruption of seabed morphology	M	Erosion reduction of shoreline morphology	M
									Change in erosion/deposition patterns	M
Biological Effects			Benthic Communities		Fish & Turtles		Marine Mammals		Birds	
			Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M
Operation	Device deployment	Physical presence of WEC device and structural components	Reef effects; Increase in productivity and biodiversity	M	Enhancement of reproduction and nursery areas; Increase in food availability	M	Increase in food availability	M	Increase in food availability	M
			Risk of harmful biofouling; Invasive species	M	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	M	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	M	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	M
		Noise generation	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	
Socioeconomic Effects			Local Communities		Archaeology Protected Sites		Landscape Seascape		Economic activities	
			Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M
Operation	Device deployment	WEC device and support structures; Energy extraction	Potential struggle for the practice of surf sports	?	NK	M	Loss of shoreline amenities; Visual Impact	M	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g. loss of fishery areas)	M
		Renewable electricity production	Clean energy supply (avoidance of GHG emissions); Education campaigns; Ecotourism; Blue Economy development	M	NK	M	NK	M	NK	M

Table 2.3: Examples of mitigation measures in different phases of a project development.

Phase	Stressor	Receptors	Mitigation Measures
Construction	Installation of WEC device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seabed - Water column - Benthic communities - Fish and turtles - Marine mammals - Birds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Works carried out on the seabed limited to the minimum required - The types of anchors (rock, latching and stabilization) chosen based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment, thus limiting the volume of drill cuttings discharged to the environment and the seabed morphology disruption - Disclose the calendar of operations and a plan of restricted areas, especially to fishermen and shipping operators
	Pile driving activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce sound pressure levels using pile caps and vibratory hammers - Attenuate the produced sound using bubble curtains, hydro sound dampers or de-watered cofferdams
Operation	Presence of the device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benthic communities - Fish and turtles - Marine mammals - Birds - Local communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use non-toxic antifouling coatings - Delineation of a safety zone, where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of cetaceans within that area - Promote environmental awareness in the region

Table 2.4: Monitoring techniques/protocols.

Monitoring Techniques/protocols	Code	Monitoring Techniques/protocols	Code
Acoustic doppler current profiler (ADCP)	1	Radar observations (birds)	14
Active acoustic – SONARS	2	ROVs, underwater cameras	15
Aerial photographs	3	Sampling collection and analysis techniques	16
Analytical methods (e.g. econometric models)	4	Satellite images	17
Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD)	5	Secchi disk method	18
Desk based analysis	6	Sonar and LIDAR techniques	19
Dive surveys	7	Spectrophotometry, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) or fluorometry	20
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	8	Telemetry tags	21
Hydrophones	9	Temperature sensors	22
In situ multiparametric probes	10	Turbidity meters	23
Observation surveys	11	Use of models	24
Participatory methods (e.g. questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)	12	Wave measuring buoys	25
Passive acoustic – C-Pods	13	Winkler method and oxygen sensors	26

Table 2.5: Example of a decision tree to select monitoring techniques for the physical receptors.

Physical factor	The receptor is	
	Hydrodynamic System	Go to A
	Water Column	Go to B
	Seabed	Go to C
	Shoreline	Go to D
(A) The parameter is	Wave climate	1, 25
	Currents	1
	Turbulence	1
	Bathymetry	2, 19
(B) The parameter is	Turbidity levels	18, 23
	Temperature, salinity, and depth	5, 10, 22
	Chlorophyll α	20
	Dissolved oxygen levels	10, 26
	Nutrients and contaminants content	10
(C) The parameter is	Sediment composition and granulometry	16
	Sediment transport	23
	Contaminants content	16
(D) The parameter is	Erosion/deposition patterns	3, 17, 24
	Shoreline morphology	3, 17, 24

3 MEGAROLLER EIA AND SEIA TOOL (ESIAT)

3.1 Development of the ESIAT

The aim of the present document is to integrate the MegaRoller EIA and SEIA model into a tool – *Environmental and Socioeconomic Impact Assessment Tool (ESIAT)* – and to apply it to the MegaRoller project.

Further literature review was carried out to support the review done for D2.6. That included latest published papers, especially concerning some of the effects and mitigation measures, and papers not as recent but which present relevant alternative points of view (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1: Reviewed literature addressing environmental and socioeconomic impacts from MRE projects.

Topic	Author	Description
Hydrodynamics	Iglesias and Carballo, 2014 Venugopal et al., 2017 Nuernberg and Tao 2018 O’Dea et al., 2019	Effects on hydrodynamics, such as wave height and sedimentation rate
EMFs	Gill et al., 2014 Hutchison et al., 2020	Effects on marine mammals and fish
Noise	De Backer and Hostens, 2017	Effects on marine mammals, fish, and birds
Physical presence of equipment/structures	Adams et al., 2014 Coates et al., 2014 De Mesel et al., 2015 Dunham et al., 2015 Krone et al., 2017 Van Hal et al., 2017 Kraus and Carter, 2018 Sheehan et al. 2018 Taormina et al., 2018 Birchenough and Degraer, 2020 Coolen et al., 2020	Effects in benthic habitats and communities Effects in biodiversity and ecosystem health Effects in fisheries Effects from decommissioning
Socioeconomic	Chozas et al., 2010 Bonar et al., 2015 Dalton et al., 2015	Effects on local communities and economic activities Public acceptability of MRE projects
Several topics	Simas et al. 2013b Dannheim et al., 2019 Mendoza et al., 2019 Copping and Hemery, 2020 Vinagre et al., 2020	Varied topics covering environmental and socioeconomic effects

Although the set of studies reviewed for this Deliverable corroborates largely with D2.6, the relevant alternative points of view allowed to refine some of the information included in the previous deliverable. This included removing/adding/redefining activities, stressors, or effects, and redefining the magnitude scaling of the impacts.

The most expressive change to the information presented on D2.6 was the redefinition of the negative impacts magnitude and their range of magnitudes. To do so, each negative effect related to a stressor was evaluated for its magnitude by four researchers to whom was asked to assign a value from 1-low importance to 5-high importance, relating to a “least impacting scenario” and a “major impacting scenario”, respectively. This would allow setting the range of magnitudes of an impact. For example, the Stressor “chemical/oil/fuel spill” coming from any activities will have a different impact magnitude if we consider common fuel release to sea during normal vessel manoeuvres (least impacting scenario) or if a major oil spill from an unexpected leakage or from an accident occurs (major impact scenario). Another example is for the Stressor “visual impact”, which may have different impact magnitudes if the activity which poses the stressor is well accepted (least impacting scenario) or very badly accepted (major impacting scenario) by local communities. Finally, a set of 6 classes of impacts, including positive impacts and 5 classes of negative (revised) impacts, was generated (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2: Classes of impact magnitude encompassed in the ESIAT.

Magnitude of impact	Range of values	Description	
		Environmental	Socioeconomic
Major	4.5-5	Degradation to the quality or availability of habitats and/or wildlife with expected recovery taking more than 5 years.	Change to commercial activity leading to a great loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Potential mid-term effect upon public health/well-being, real risk of injury.
High	3.5-4.5	Degradation to the quality or availability of habitats and/or wildlife with expected recovery taking more than 2 years.	Change to commercial activity leading to a loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Potential short-term effect upon public health/well-being, real risk of injury.
Moderate	2.5-3.5	Change in habitats or species beyond natural variability with expected recovery within 2 years.	Change to commercial activity leading to a loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Possible, but not likely effect upon public health/well-being, remote risk of injury.
Low	1.5-2.5	Change from baseline conditions measurable but within scale of natural variability.	Possible nuisance to other activities and some minor influence on income or opportunity. Nuisance, but no lasting effect upon public health/well-being.
Negligible	1-1.5	Change in habitats or species within scope of existing variability and difficult to measure or observe	Noticed by, but not a nuisance to other commercial activities. No discernible effects upon the health and well-being of the public.
Positive	-	An enhancement of ecosystem or popular parameter.	Benefits to local community.

3.2 Layout and functioning of the ESIAT

The tool is presented as an Excel file to simplify the arrangement of information and, most importantly, to allow adjustment of the assessment throughout the EIA process, following the adoption of an AM approach. The AM considers changes in the project impacts and their respective mitigation measures as well as the adjustment of the monitoring plan, according to monitoring results, thus allowing the monitoring of the effectiveness of implemented mitigation measures and, if required, the update of the magnitude classification of impacts, the definition of a new set of mitigation measures, and the adjustment of the monitoring plan.

The Excel file will also allow adding input of new information and applying it to other MRE projects in the future.

In the Excel file were included nine parameters, each one set in a different column:

- i) Project development phase.
- ii) Activity (which poses Stressors).
- iii) Stressor (which has key Effects on the Receptors).
- iv) Receptor.
- v) Effect.
- vi) Magnitude of the impacts.
- vii) Mitigation measures to the impacts.
- viii) Monitoring parameters.
- ix) Monitoring techniques.

In different rows is presented the information pertaining to each parameter.

Initially, the application of filters to each column, which is the basis of the final tool, allows the user to select the parameters of interest and obtain information about the activities undertaken, how they might affect the receptor and the magnitude of the impact, and how to monitor the impact by applying specific parameters and techniques.

The final tool was designed with the goal of being clear and user friendly. To use it, the users will follow three simple steps in the main sheet – “Task-search Tool” (Figure 3.1).

- 1) Choose the project development phase(s) (from “A. Preparation” to “D. Decommissioning”).
- 2) Choose the environmental/socioeconomic receptor(s) (from “1. Hydrodynamics” to “12. Economic activities”).
- 3) Export the information requested as a PDF file by clicking where prompted (“Click HERE to export as PDF”). The PDF file (Annex 1) will include the information for the nine parameters mentioned above ordered by project development stage and receptor.

Because Step 1 gives lettered options (for example, “A. Preparation”) and Step 2 gives numbered options (for example, “5. Biological - Benthic communities”), it is recommended that the PDF file is saved with the corresponding designation to ease consultation later (as A5, in the case of selecting the two options mentioned above).

Some aspects need to be considered to the correct functioning of the tool:

- Allow macros when opening the file.

- In the “Task-search Tool” sheet select the minimum of one option both in “Step 1” and “Step 2” for the data to be correctly filtered.

If the user needs to add more information to the tool:

- In the sheet “Task-search Tool” select the fields to which the new data will be added (e.g., “A. Preparation” + “5. Biological – Benthic communities”).
- In the sheet “Effects and magnitude”, the information for the selected fields will be shown. Insert the new information in a new line between any two lines in the table.
- To edit the impacts magnitude scores, place the new scores in the “Impact” columns and the magnitude colours will be updated.

Figure 3.1: ESIAT “task-search” menu layout.

4 MEGAROLLER OVERALL IMPACT APPRAISAL

The application of the ESIAT to the MegaRoller installation³ rendered a complex and extensive document that includes the potential environmental and socioeconomic impacts expected from the MegaRoller installation and their mitigation measures (as well as monitoring parameters and techniques) (Annex 1). This section presents a summary of the impacts which potentially have greater significance, and the reader is addressed to the full assessment in Annex 1.

Overall, the expected potential impacts and their magnitude are similar to those coming from other OE installations. While many of the potential impacts are negative impacts some positive impacts are also expected (e.g., artificial reef effect enhancing local biodiversity; new opportunities for businesses enhancement or development new ones, and employment enhancement).

At present, the negative impacts with greater significance are expected during the preparation and construction phases (Figure 4.1).

Preparatory activities of dredging and seabed levelling (low to high magnitude) may lead to disruption of the seabed morphology and deterioration of sediment quality, although these effects should be temporary. During the construction phase, the installation (laying on the seabed) of the WEC device and support structures (including the electrical cable, moorings, and anchors) should have minimal impact on the seabed. However, during both phases, those activities may lead to disruption of the benthic communities and death of organisms (e.g., by crushing) (moderate to high magnitude), leading to loss of diversity and productivity which may take much longer to mitigate (potentially years). Although the timeframe of recovery is uncertain and difficult to distinguish from natural variability (Kraus and Carter, 2018; Sheehan et al., 2018; Taormina et al., 2018), the artificial reef effect produced by the MegaRoller installation during the operational phase will create the opportunity for organisms to settle, grow, and reproduce, thus allowing for a more rapid recovery of the communities.

For these activities, mitigation comes by preventing or minimizing the effects, and it includes:

- a. Prior to the activities
 - i) Using mathematical model simulations to predict impacts;
 - ii) Selecting areas that cause the least environmental damage;
 - iii) Analysing the sediment and water quality and contamination level in surrounding areas.
- b. During the activities
 - i) Limiting the works carried out on the seabed to the minimum required;
 - ii) Reducing the seabed area to be cleared to the minimum possible;
 - iii) Reducing the moorings and electrical cable paths to minimum areas;
 - iv) Choosing anchors based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment (thus limiting the volume of drill cuttings discharged to the environment and disruption of the seabed morphology);
 - v) Using silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments.

Additionally to the effects on the seabed and benthic communities, during the preparation phase there may be impact (low to high magnitude) by sonar or seismic surveys on pelagic organisms such as fish,

³ Considering the current characteristics of the technology and support structures, and the foreseen deployment site in Peniche (Portugal).

turtles, and mammals, with potential disruption of their behaviour or even physical harm. To mitigate these impacts, it should be considered:

- a. Delineating safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of animals within that area;
- b. Soft start ('ramp up') to allow organisms to evade the area;
- c. Using silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments.

Apart from the impacts mentioned above, it should be highlighted the potential impact expected on local communities and local businesses (low to moderate magnitude). For example, during the preparation and construction phases the project development may be negatively perceived by its potential impacts on the environment and on local commercial activities (e.g., fishing). During the operation phase, the installations require an extensive section of the maritime space which may pose restrictions for sea users, namely the local communities and businesses that rely on fishing as their sole or primary income. Hence, in common to other MRE projects, social acceptance will be crucial to develop MegaRoller.

Social acceptance is generally achieved by promoting strong public participation during all phases of a project, ideally with early discussions and providing information previous to the project implementation.

The mitigation of this impact includes:

- a. Promoting strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers, and scientists through participatory methods (e.g., meetings, questionnaires/surveys), during all phases of the project;
- b. Favouring the acquisition of workers and materials within the local community, during all phases of the project;
- c. Providing monetary compensation to make up for the reduced income from fishing, during the operational phase.

Figure 4.1: Example of the ESIAT results showing the impacts potentially reaching greater magnitude (from Low to High magnitude).

MegaRoller		WavEC		Impact assessment results				Impact Magnitude Key:		
								Major High	Moderate Low	Negligible Positive
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology	GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology	Active acoustics – SONARs		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Sediment movement	Modelling		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project	None in particular	Modelling		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Analyse the sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology	GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology	Active acoustics – SONARs		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Sediment movement	Modelling		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project	None in particular	Modelling		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and biomass)	Modelling		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Turbidity	In situ probes		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Temperature	In situ probes		
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Temperature	In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting		

(Continues in the next page).

Figure 4.1: Continued.

A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Chlorophyll a	In situ probes
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Chlorophyll a	Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Dissolved oxygen	In situ probes
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Dissolved oxygen	Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Nutrients	In situ probes
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Nutrients	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Water contaminants	In situ probes
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Water contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Soft start ('ramp up') to allow organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of animals within that area	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Soft start ('ramp up') to allow organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of animals within that area	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		The various types of anchors (rock, latching and stabilization) should be chosen based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment, thus limiting the volume of drill cuttings discharged to the environment and disruption of the seabed morphology	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Reduce the cable path to minimum areas	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular

5 FINAL REMARKS

There are many gaps in knowledge about the potential impacts (particularly environmental impacts) from WE projects, as a consequence of the reduced spatial scale (for example, number and arrangement of devices) and temporal scale (duration of the project) that allow for effects to be noticeable and impacts to be measurable. These scales also make cumulative impacts especially difficult to assess. This is because many effects are perceived effects on receptors and are not measured effects.

The lack of information may on the one hand result in underestimating the impacts, which may prevent the mitigation measures to be applied effectively after a point of no return is reached. On the other hand, it often results in overestimating the impacts, leading to conservative approaches in implementing MRE projects which may delay or prevent the development of MRE projects and of the MRE sector in general. Thus, it is crucial to develop environmental monitoring programmes around the devices that are operating or that will be installed, allowing the collection of more data and the optimization of modelling the impacts. Because the OE sector is fairly recent, gathering information from other sectors (such as the Offshore Wind and the Oil & Gas sectors) which have been working at sea for much longer time might also be useful. Although uncertainty is present it is also acknowledged, therefore creating room for discussion and to potentially redefine the routine monitoring programmes and mitigation requirements if the new information about impacts indicate that they have been underestimated or overestimated. This is the principle of Adaptive Management.

The Environmental and Socioeconomic Impact Assessment Tool (ESIAT) presented here was developed considering potential impacts from MegaRoller to environmental and socioeconomic receptors. Similarly to other research on impact assessment, it may suffer from the paucity of demonstrable information that allows to accurately estimate impacts and quantify its magnitude. For example, the magnitudes suggested at present were the result of an evaluation of expected effects by four researchers which on one hand account for different perspectives, but which might also produce a wide range of magnitude for a particular impact. In the sense of Adaptive Management, the magnitude of impacts, as well as the thresholds between magnitude classes, should be re-evaluated when more monitoring data is available and should be redefined if needed.

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7 ANNEXES

Annex 1: MegaRoller environmental and socioeconomic impact assessment.

Impact assessment results

Major	Moderate	Negligible
High	Low	Positive

Phase	Activity	Stressor	Receptor	Key effect	Impact	Mitigation Measures	Monitoring parameter	Monitoring Technique
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	2. Physical - Water column	Disruption and littering of surface waters		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Analyse the water quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging	Depth; Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	Desk based analysis; In situ probes; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	Modelling	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology; Sediment movement	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARS; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	Sediment movement	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Analyse the sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	4. Physical - Shoreline	Disruption and littering of shoreline		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular

A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	4. Physical - Shoreline	Changes in the material added to/removed from shoreline, affecting local topography		Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	4. Physical - Shoreline	Changes in the material added to/removed from shoreline, affecting local topography		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	4. Physical - Shoreline	Changes in the material added to/removed from shoreline, affecting local topography		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology; Sediment movement	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARs; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and biomass)	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratory and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Analyse the water quality and contamination level near the seabed prior to dredging	Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	In situ probes; Desk based analysis; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratory and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Soft start ('ramp up') to allow organisms (benthic fish) to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology; Sediment movement	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARs; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project	None in particular	Modelling

A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and biomass)	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Analyse the water quality and contamination level along the water column prior to dredging	Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	In situ probes; Desk based analysis; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Soft start ('ramp up') to allow organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of animals within that area	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Select areas that cause the least environmental damage prior to dredging	Seabed morphology; Sediment movement	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARS; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and presence/absence) and distribution	Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Analyse the water quality and contamination level along the water column prior to dredging	Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	In situ probes; Desk based analysis; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Soft start ('ramp up') to allow organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular

A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of animals within that area	None in particular	Modelling
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	8. Biological - Birds	Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	8. Biological - Birds	Disruption of behaviour		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods); Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Risk of collision with sea users		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise	None in particular	None in particular

A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Identification and avoidance of Archaeological / Protected sites previous to activities	Presence of Archaeological / Protected sites	Desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARs; Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs, AUVs), followed by desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Identification and avoidance of Archaeological / Protected sites previous to activities	Presence of Archaeological / Protected sites	GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual Impact		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular; Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Modelling; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular; Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Modelling; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Reduce the number and size of vessels to minimum required	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)

A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods) ; Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
A. Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
A. Preparation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Hazards to navigation; Potential disruption to economic activities		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
A. Preparation	Surveying	Sonar / Seismic surveys	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
A. Preparation	Surveying	Vessel activity	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Deterioration of water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Deterioration of water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	2. Physical - Water column	Disruption and littering of surface waters		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Analyse the water quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to the activities	Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	In situ probes; Desk based analysis; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses

B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	2. Physical - Water column	Disruption of pelagic habitats		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		The various types of anchors (rock, latching and stabilization) should be chosen based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment, thus limiting the volume of drill cuttings discharged to the environment and disruption of the seabed morphology	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Reduce the cable path to minimum areas	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	4. Physical - Shoreline	Disruption and littering of shoreline		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	4. Physical - Shoreline	Changes in the material added to/removed from shoreline, affecting local topography		Reduce the cable path to minimum areas	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		The various types of anchors (rock, latching and stabilization) should be chosen based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment, thus limiting the volume of drill cuttings discharged to the environment and disruption of the seabed morphology	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Reduce the cable path to minimum areas	None in particular	Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms; Loss of biodiversity; Reduction in productivity		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular

B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from noise; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from noise; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from noise; Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from noise		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from noise		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm from noise		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	8. Biological - Birds	Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	8. Biological - Birds	Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	8. Biological - Birds	Disruption of behaviour		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)

B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods) ; Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Risk of collision with sea users		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Interdiction to sea use for locals; Local disturbance; Noise disturbance		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Interdiction to sea use for locals; Local disturbance; Noise disturbance		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Interdiction to sea use for locals; Local disturbance; Noise disturbance		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Interdiction to sea use for locals; Local disturbance; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Noise disturbance		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Identification and avoidance of Archaeological / Protected sites previous to activities	Presence of Archaeological/Protected sites	Desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARs; Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs, AUVs), followed by desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling

B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual Impact		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular; Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Modelling; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Maintain the site clean and ensure its restoration after the activities (onshore)	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Reduce the number and size of vessels to minimum required	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods) ; Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
B. Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Hazards to navigation; Potential disruption to economic activities		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Installation of WEC device and support structures	Installation of WEC, electrical cable, moorings and anchors	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)

B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Avoid construction activities during sensitive periods such as busy tourist seasons	None in particular	Desk based analysis
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Presence of machinery/equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Maintain the site clean and ensure its restoration after the activities (onshore)	None in particular	None in particular
B. Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	1. Physical - Hydrodynamics	Reduction of wave action		Monitor currents and turbulence	Waves (height, period, mean direction, and directional spreading); Currents (speed, direction and velocity profile along the water column); Turbulence; Bathymetry	Desk based analysis; ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler); Wave measuring buoys; Active acoustics – SONARs
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Deterioration of water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Deterioration of water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	2. Physical - Water column	Disruption and littering of surface waters		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbulence		Monitor water quality	Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	In situ probes; Desk based analysis; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Monitor sediment quality	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Monitor changes in sediment deposition and in seabed morphology	Sediment composition and granulometry	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Monitor sediment composition	Sediment composition and granulometry	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	4. Physical - Shoreline	Disruption and littering of shoreline		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	4. Physical - Shoreline	Change in erosion/ deposition patterns		Monitor sediment quality	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	4. Physical - Shoreline	Change in erosion/ deposition patterns		Monitor changes in sediment deposition and in shoreline morphology	Sediment composition and granulometry	Modelling
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	4. Physical - Shoreline	Change in erosion/ deposition patterns		Monitor sediment composition	Sediment composition and granulometry	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses

C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	4. Physical - Shoreline	Potential reduction of shoreline erosion		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour		Avoid sensitive and protected areas	None in particular	Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs, AUVs), followed by desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour		Use adequate cable configuration and sheath/armouring to reduce EMFs emission	None in particular	Modelling
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour		Increase the distance from the cable to the overlying water whenever possible by burying the cables in the seabed and covering them with boulders, concrete mattresses or other cover material	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Reef effects; Increase in biodiversity and productivity		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Risk of harmful biofouling (e.g., non-native species)		Monitor communities; Remove non-native species from the area, also prevent settlement as biofouling	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and biomass), distribution, presence of non-native species; Species composition, diversity, abundance (density, biomass, coverage), distribution, presence of non-native species	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses; Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs, AUVs), followed by desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Risk of harmful biofouling (e.g., non-native species)		Use non-toxic antifouling techniques	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Risk of harmful biofouling (e.g., non-native species)		Promote environmental awareness in the region	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour		Avoid sensitive and protected areas	None in particular	Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs, AUVs), followed by desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour		Use adequate cable configuration and sheath/armouring to reduce EMFs emission	None in particular	Modelling
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour		Increase the distance from the cable to the overlying water whenever possible by burying the cables in the seabed and covering them with boulders, concrete mattresses or other cover material	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Noise generation (from device or sweeping of electrical cable/moorings)	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device, structural components and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Increase in food availability; Enhancement of reproduction and nursery areas		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed

C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Monitor communities	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density) and distribution; Species presence and abundance (density and biomass); Species presence and abundance (density); Species distribution	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses; Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs, AUVs), followed by desk based analysis; Desk based analysis; Active acoustics – SONARs; Telemetry tags
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of turtles within that area	None in particular	Modelling
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Promote environmental awareness in the region	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Avoid sensitive and protected areas	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Use adequate cable configuration and sheath/armouring to reduce EMFs emission	None in particular	Modelling
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Electromagnetic fields	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour		Increase the distance from the cable to the overlying water whenever possible by burying the cables in the seabed and covering them with boulders, concrete mattresses or other cover material	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Noise generation (from device or moorings)	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Increase in food availability		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Monitor communities	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and presence/absence) and distribution	Desk based analysis; Observation surveys; Passive acoustics – C-Pods; Telemetry tags
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of cetaceans within that area	None in particular	Modelling
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Promote environmental awareness in the region	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	8. Biological - Birds	Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	8. Biological - Birds	Increase in food availability		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	8. Biological - Birds	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Promote environmental awareness in the region	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	8. Biological - Birds	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment		Monitor communities	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density) and distribution	Desk based analysis; Observation surveys; RADAR techniques; Telemetry tags; Ringing techniques
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	8. Biological - Birds	Disruption of behaviour		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular

C. Operation	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods); Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Risk of collision with sea users		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential struggle for the practice of surf sports		Perform maintenance of signaling devices of the restricted area at sea and on land	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential struggle for the practice of surf sports		Promote environmental awareness in the region	Level of public acceptance	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential struggle for the practice of surf sports		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Renewable electricity production	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Clean energy supply (avoidance of GHG emissions); Education campaigns; Ecotourism; Blue Economy development		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual Impact		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular

C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual Impact		Implement the project far away from the coastline (as possible) and have all equipment (except for marking buoys necessary to identify the project area) placed submerged (as possible)	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Reduce the number and size of vessels to minimum required	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods); Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
C. Operation	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
C. Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Hazards to navigation; Potential disruption to economic activities		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Presence of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Promotion of leisure activities (e.g., recreational scuba diving) and ecotourism		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	Presence of WEC device and support structures	Renewable electricity production	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Clean energy supply (avoidance of GHG emissions); Education campaigns; Ecotourism; Blue Economy development		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
C. Operation	Operations and Maintenance activities	Vessel activity	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	1. Physical - Hydrodynamics	Increase in wave action to historical trend		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Deterioration of water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	2. Physical - Water column	Deterioration of water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	2. Physical - Water column	Disruption and littering of surface waters		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular

D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Analyse the water quality and contamination level in the project area	Turbidity; Temperature; Salinity; Chlorophyll a; Dissolved oxygen; Nutrients; Water contaminants	In situ probes; Desk based analysis; In situ CTD (Conductivity/Temperature/Depth) casting; Water sampling and laboratory probes; Water sampling and laboratory spectrophotometry or fluorometry analysis; Water sampling and laboratory probes or Winkler method; Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	2. Physical - Water column	Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	3. Physical - Seabed	Deterioration of sediment quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Analyse the sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging	Sediment composition and granulometry; Sediment organic matter; Sediment contaminants	Sampling, followed by laboratorial and desk based analyses
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	3. Physical - Seabed	Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	4. Physical - Shoreline	Deterioration of sediment and water quality		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	4. Physical - Shoreline	Disruption and littering of shoreline		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	4. Physical - Shoreline	Change in erosion/deposition patterns to historical trend		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Loss of biodiversity, biomass, and productivity enhanced locally		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Loss of biodiversity, biomass, and productivity enhanced locally		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Loss of biodiversity, biomass, and productivity enhanced locally		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	5. Biological - Benthic communities	Loss of biodiversity, biomass, and productivity enhanced locally		Check feasibility of keeping structures as artificial reefs	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular

D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour; Loss of reproduction and nursery areas		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour; Loss of reproduction and nursery areas		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour; Loss of reproduction and nursery areas		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour; Loss of reproduction and nursery areas		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour; Loss of reproduction and nursery areas		Check feasibility of keeping structures as artificial reefs	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	6. Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration)	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Check feasibility of keeping structures as artificial reefs	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	7. Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour; Potential physical harm; Potential harm from noise		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	8. Biological - Birds	Potential toxic response		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	8. Biological - Birds	Potential harm through collision and entanglement		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	8. Biological - Birds	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	8. Biological - Birds	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	8. Biological - Birds	Decrease in food availability; Disruption of behaviour		Check feasibility of keeping structures as artificial reefs	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	8. Biological - Birds	Disruption of behaviour		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and give opportunity to organisms to evade the area	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)

D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods) ; Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Risk of collision with sea users		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Lower vessel speed to reduce noise	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	9. Socioeconomic - Local communities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users; Noise disturbance		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	10. Socioeconomic - Archaeological / Protected sites	Potential disruption of preserved traces		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual Impact		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular; Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Modelling; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	11. Socioeconomic - Landscape/Seascape	Visual impact		Reduce the number and size of vessels to minimum required	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Employment enhancement		No action needed	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones)	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)

D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	New opportunities for company creation and development		No action needed	Number of new businesses created	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		No action needed	Identification of relevant stakeholders	Desk based analysis; Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Level of public acceptance; Quantification of avoided GHG emissions	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods); Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models)
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Project development in the region	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect directly on commercial activities (e.g., fishing)		Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Desk based analysis; GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, followed by desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities	None in particular	Desk based analysis
D. Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Potential disruption to economic activities		Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Hazards to navigation; Potential disruption to economic activities		Recover the equipment immediately after it has been observed drifting/sinking	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	Desk based analysis; Modelling
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Noise should be limited to the minimum required	None in particular	None in particular
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Enhancement of fishery areas		No action needed	No action needed	No action needed
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Removal of WEC device and support structures	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
D. Decommissioning	Removal of WEC device and support structures	Vessel activity	12. Socioeconomic - Economic activities	Maritime spatial restrictions for sea users		Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community	None in particular	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)